

A Comparative Study of HbA1c Levels and Serum Ferritin among Iron Deficient Anemic Pregnant Women and Normal Pregnant Women in a Tertiary Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Iron deficiency anemia is the most common cause of anemia. Pregnancy is usually associated with anemia, and additionally in late pregnancy, iron deficiency anemia is seen which is caused by increase in iron demands. HbA1c is affected by several factors including pregnancy.

Objective: To estimate HbA1C and serum ferritin levels and compare them among Iron deficient anemic pregnant women and normal pregnant women

Methods: Comparative cross-sectional study was performed on 100 patients, among which 50 were Iron deficient Anemic (IDA) pregnant women and 50 were normal pregnant women, attending obstetrics OP, GGH, Ananthapuramu. Detailed history of patient, clinical examination was done. Laboratory parameters estimated were HbA1c, serum ferritin, complete blood count, and fasting blood sugar. Pregnant women aged 18-35 years and those willing to give consent were included in the study. Pregnant women with a known H/o Diabetes, Hemoglobinopathy, Chronic liver and kidney disease were excluded from the study.

Institutional ethical committee clearance was obtained.

Results: In the current study mean±S.D levels of HbA1c was 4.54 ± 0.66 in control group, while in cases was 6.21 ± 0.36 . The difference was statistically significant (p value <0.05). In our study, among cases HbA1c inversely correlated with serum ferritin (r value -0.336 and p value <0.05).

Conclusion: The present study concluded that the levels of HbA1c were increased significantly among patients with iron deficiency anaemia. So, Iron deficiency anaemia has to be kept in mind before taking into consideration HbA1c levels to diagnose diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: Iron deficiency Anemia (IDA), HbA1c, Ferritin.

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Introduction

Anemia is a condition in which the number of red cells necessary to meet the body's physiological requirements is insufficient. Iron deficiency anemia is due to the lack of sufficient iron to form normal red blood cells. It is the most common cause of anemia worldwide and also the most common anemia occurring during pregnancy. Pregnancy is usually associated with dilutional anemia, and additionally in late pregnancy, iron deficiency anemia is seen which is caused by increase in iron demands. Diagnosis of iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) requires demonstration of low blood haemoglobin (Hb) in the presence of depleted iron

stores. Serum ferritin is the most sensitive non-invasive indicator of iron stores but its utility is compromised in inflammatory states as it is an acute phase reactant [2]. Ferritin is the storage form of iron, and it reflects the iron status accurately [3]. Serum ferritin levels in pregnant women are decreased due to hemodilution. Diagnosis of IDA in pregnant women is usually performed using the serum ferritin [4]. A ferritin concentration <15g/L in adults is diagnostic of iron deficiency. An elevated ferritin may reflect iron overload; however, ferritin is an acute phase protein, so may also be increased in liver disease, malignancy,

infection and inflammation [5]. Therefore, a normal ferritin concentration alone does not necessarily exclude iron deficiency. Diabetes mellitus is one of the most common diseases worldwide with significant morbidity and mortality. HbA1c remains one of the most important methods for diagnosis and monitoring of the disease. Since HbA1c is a reflection of the glucose attached to red blood cells, factors affecting hemoglobin and red blood cells' half-life can influence HbA1c measurements. Glycated hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) is a major part of HbA1 and comprises approximately 5% of the total hemoglobin non-diabetic individuals. It provides a better estimate of average glycemic control than routine determinations of blood glucose concentration and is the most widely used index of chronic glycaemia. Currently, HbA1c is widely used for the target value of glycemic control or for diagnosis of diabetes mellitus, the gold standard indicator of glycemic control [6]. HbA1c is influenced by a variety of physical factors and it may not reflect glycemic control accurately. Such factors include shortened erythrocyte lifespan, such as by bleeding, hemolytic anemia, renal anemia, extended erythrocyte lifespan, such as by vitamin B12 deficiency, or variant hemoglobin [7,8,9,10]. HbA1c is known to increase in late pregnancy [11,12]. It showed to be increased in iron deficiency anemia as compared to glycemia in patients [13]. Some authors have also found that on supplementation with iron therapy, there was a significant decrease in the levels of glycated hemoglobin. It has been suggested that the HbA1c level does not only reflect glycaemia, but also that it is sensitive to alterations in Hb concentration.

Aim: To compare the HbA1C levels and serum ferritin levels among iron deficient anemic pregnant women and normal pregnant women.

Objective:

1. To estimate HbA1C levels and serum ferritin in iron deficient anemic pregnant women and normal pregnant women.
2. To compare HbA1C levels and serum ferritin among iron deficient anemic pregnant women and normal pregnant women.

Materials & Methods

This study was conducted on 100 patients, among which 50 pregnant women with iron deficiency anemia were included as cases and other 50 normal pregnant women as control group, attending Obstetrics OP, GGH, and Ananthapuram. It was a comparative cross-sectional study. Institution ethical committee clearance was obtained. After

fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria, an informed written consent was obtained from the patients. Medical and obstetrics history (age, parity, gestational age) was recorded for each participant using questionnaire. Weight and height were measured using the standard methods and Body Mass Index (BMI) was computed as kg/m². Detailed history taking, clinical examination was done for both cases and controls. Biochemical examination was performed on HbA1c, serum ferritin and Fasting blood sugar. **INCLUSION CRITERIA:** Pregnant women aged 18-35 years and those who were willing to give consent were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with a known H/o Diabetes, Hemoglobinopathy, Chronic liver disease, chronic kidney disease, Hyperbilirubinemia, Acute blood loss, Vitamin B12 and folic acid deficiency, anemia due to causes other than Iron Deficiency were excluded from the study.

Sample Collection: Under sterile conditions, 5ml of venous blood sample was collected and aliquoted into a plain tube and EDTA tube for estimation of biochemical parameters and hemogram respectively. Biochemical parameters like, HbA1C and Fasting blood glucose were analysed in fully auto analyzer (AU 480-Beckmann Coulter). Serum ferritin levels were estimated on semi auto analyser using commercially available kits.

Statistical Analysis: The descriptive data was presented in mean Standard deviation. The difference between two groups is tested using unpaired T-Test. Pearson correlation coefficient(r) was used to determine the association between ferritin and HbA1C levels. P-value of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), anemia is defined as hemoglobin (Hb) levels <12.0 g/dL in women. The normal range for ferritin in our blood serum is 24 to 307 ng/mL for adult females. Normal HbA1c is < 5.7%, levels between 5.7–6.4% are considered prediabetes, and a level of > 6.5% is diagnostic for diabetes.

Results

Our study included 50 iron deficient anemic pregnant women and 50 normal pregnant women. The mean age of IDA group was (25.66±5.01). The mean age of control group was (26.7±6.05) the mean of HbA1c in IDA group and control group were (6.21±0.36, 4.54±0.66) respectively. This result showed that there were significantly increased (p < 0.05) of HbA1c levels among IDA group compared to control group.

Figure 1: Comparison of various parameters among IDA cases and controls

Table 1: Mean±S.D values of various parameters among cases and controls

Parameters	Cases	Controls	P Value	Significance (S)/(NS)
Age	25.66±5.01	26.7±6.06	0.3515	NS
Hemoglobin (gm/dL)	8.94±1.79	10.38±1.13	0.0001	S
MCV (mg/dL)	75.66±10.32	87.71±13.06	0.0001	S
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	16.23±7.23	75.19±24.24	0.0001	S
HbA1C (%)	6.21±0.36	4.54±0.66	0.0001	S
FBS (mg/dL)	96.94±11.42	102.04±17.38	0.0860	NS

Figure 2: Correlation between Hba1c and Serum Ferritin among Cases:

Table 2: r- value and P-value among cases:

	r value	P-value	Significant
HbA1C and Serum Ferritin	-0.336	<0.05	Yes

Discussion

HbA1c provides valuable information about the average blood glucose level of individuals over a period of three months. Besides blood glucose, HbA1c levels can be affected by conditions unrelated to diabetes like anaemia. The most frequent type of anaemia is iron deficiency anaemia. Iron deficiency is responsible for roughly half of all anaemia cases in India. Despite the lengthy life span of erythrocytes, the concentration of glycated haemoglobin has been found to be higher in anaemic patients.

Our study included 50 iron deficient anaemic pregnant women and 50 normal pregnant women. In our study Mean \pm S.D of age among IDA group was 25.66 ± 5.01 (Table: No:1, Figure: No: 1). The mean age of control group was 26.7 ± 6.05 . The Mean \pm S.D of HbA1c in IDA group and control group were 6.21 ± 0.36 and 4.54 ± 0.66 respectively (Table: No:1, Figure: No: 1) and p value was statistically significant. This is in accordance to the study of Coban and colleagues who reported that HbA1c showed high levels in patients with iron deficiency anemia [14]. Basil A. Alzahrani, et al study found a significant increase in HbA1c levels in iron deficiency anemia and sickle cell disease in patients not known to have diabetes [15]. Similarly, in a study conducted by Shanthi B et al [16] the mean HbA1c of cases were 7.6, compared to 5.5 in healthy controls. They hypothesized that serum iron and ferritin levels were inversely related to HbA1c levels, and that HbA1c levels tend to be higher in the presence of iron deficiency anemia. Christy et al [17]. Found that the mean HbA1c of cases was 6.87, while it was 5.65 in healthy controls. They hypothesized that serum iron and ferritin levels were related to higher HbA1c levels.

According to some studies, there were no differences between HbA1c levels of anemia patients and controls. Study done by El-Agouza L et al [18] showed that HbA1c level were higher in patients with iron deficiency anemia and decreased significantly upon treatment with iron. Recently Sinha et al showed that HbA1c levels and absolute HbA1c levels increased with treatment of iron deficiency anemia [19]. Rai and Pattabiraman [20] conducted a study to evaluate different methods used to analyze HbA1c and found no significant difference between them.

However, in a study by Tarim et al. [21], the results were inconclusive with some subjects showing elevation in A1C, while some showed no elevation. In a study carried out by Hashimoto et al [22], HbA1C levels were elevated in pregnant diabetic women. In a report of the Japanese Society of Diabetes and Pregnancy [23], the authors reported that HbA1c tends to decrease during the first and second trimesters, followed by an increase during

the last trimester of gestation, in an analysis of 136 normal pregnant women.

In our study, the Mean \pm S.D of Hemoglobin among cases was 8.94 ± 1.79 and among controls it was 10.38 ± 1.13 (Table: No:1, Figure: No:1). The mean \pm S.D of MCV in IDA and control group were 75.66 ± 10.32 and 87.71 ± 13.06 respectively and p- value was statistically significant (Table: No:1, Figure: No:1). This is in accordance with a study done by Nitin Sinha et al [18], saying that values of HbA1c decreasing with fall in haemoglobin values and increases with iron treatment. The reason given was the study population belongs to low socioeconomic status and cause of iron deficiency was nutritional deficiency rather than malabsorption and bleeding. However, no correlation was observed after correction of anemia by oral iron supplementation for three months.

In our study, the Mean \pm S.D of Serum Ferritin among IDA group and control group were 16.23 ± 7.23 and 75.19 ± 24.24 respectively. P-value is <0.001 which is statistically significant. (Table: No:1, Figure: No:1). This is in accordance with a study done by Sharifi and Sazandeh [24], whose study did not find any significant correlation between HbA1c and ferritin in diabetic population.

In our study, the r-value and p-value among IDA group were -0.336 and <0.05 respectively (Table: No: 2, Figure: No:2), which was statistically significant. This is in accordance with the study done by Koga.M et al [25], who demonstrated that HbA1C levels increase in late pregnancy and are inversely associated with serum transferrin saturation and serum ferritin. In a study done by Kalairajan et al [26].

In 2019, showed that IDA leads to a decrease in HbA1c level with a subsequent rise in HbA1c level with its correction. This showed a positive correlation between Hb and HbA1c in IDA before treatment; In a study done by Raj and Rajan [27], ferritin showed positive correlation with HbA1c in diabetic individuals. Omar E Fadlseed et al [28], study showed absence of any association between HbA1c and IDA. It seems that there is no previous study on this topic during pregnancy. Similarly, in a study done by Alap. L et al [29], did not show any significant correlation between hemoglobin and HbA1c. In their study, the author conveyed that, Iron deficiency anemia elevates HbA1c levels in diabetic individuals with controlled plasma glucose levels. The elevation is more in patients having plasma glucose levels between 100 to 126 mg/dl and therefore, before altering the treatment regimen for diabetes, iron deficiency anemia should be kept in mind. Our study showed that there is a significant rise in HbA1C levels and decreased serum ferritin levels among Cases.

Conclusion

According to the findings in our study, there was an inverse relationship between HbA1c and mean serum Ferritin levels, and this relationship was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), i.e. mean serum ferritin decreases as HbA1c level increases. The present study concluded that the levels of HbA1c were increased significantly among patients with iron deficiency anaemia. So, Iron deficiency anaemia has to be kept in mind before using the HbA1c to diagnose diabetes.

References

- Weiss G and Goodnough LT. Anemia of chronic disease. *N Engl J Med* 2005; 352: 1011–1023.
- WHO. Serum ferritin concentrations for the assessment of iron status in individuals and populations: technical brief. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2020
- John A. Iron Deficiency and Other Hypoproliferative Anemias. In: Longo D, Fauci A, Kasper D, Hauser S, Jameson J, Loscalzo J, editors, editors. *Principles of Internal Medicine by Harrison's*. 17th ed. United States of America: McGraw-Hill; 2008. pp. 628–35.
- Amstad B.G., Krafft A., Zimmermann R., Burkhardt T. Treatment of anemia of chronic disease with true iron deficiency in pregnancy. *J. Pregnancy*. 2017; 2017:4265091.
- Gabay C and Kushner I. Acute-phase proteins and other systemic responses to inflammation. *N Engl J Med* 1999; 340: 448–454.
- American Diabetes Association Glycemic targets. *Diabetes Care*. 2017; 40:S48–S56. [PubMed] [Google Scholar] [Ref list]
- Cohen M.P., Herman W.H. Are glycosylated serum proteins ready for prime time? *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2014; 2:265–266. doi: 10.1016/S2213-8587(14)70003-8.
- Koga M., Hashimoto K., Murai J., Saito H., Mukai M., Ikegame K., Ogawa H., Kasayama S. Usefulness of glycosylated albumin as an indicator of glycemic control status in patients with hemolytic anemia. *Clin. Chim. Acta*. 2011; 412: 253–257. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2010.10.014.
- Gallagher E.J., Bloomgarden Z.T., Le Roith D. Review of hemoglobin A1c in the management of diabetes. *J. Diabetes*. 2009; 1:9–17. doi: 10.1111/j.1753-0407.2009.00009.x.
- Bry L., Chen P.C., Sacks D.B. Effects of hemoglobin variants and chemically modified derivatives on assays for glycohemoglobin. *Clin. Chem*. 2001; 47:153–163.
- Phelps R.L., Honig G.R., Green D., Metzger B.E., Frederiksen M.C., Freinkel N. Biphasic changes in hemoglobin A1c concentrations during normal human pregnancy. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol*. 1983; 147:651–653. doi: 10.1016/0002-9378(83)90443-X.
- Hiramatsu Y., Shimizu I., Omori Y., Nakabayashi M. Determination of reference intervals of glycosylated albumin and hemoglobin A1c in healthy pregnant Japanese women and analysis of their time courses and influencing factors during pregnancy. *Endocr. J*. 2012; 59:145–151. doi: 10.1507/endocrj.K10E-410.
- Hashimoto K, Noguchi S, Morimoto Y, Hamada S, Wasada K, Imai S, et al. A1C but Not Serum Glycated Albumin Is Elevated in Late Pregnancy Owing to Iron. *Diabetes*. 2008; 31(3):31–4
- Coban E., Ozdogan M., Timuragaoglu A. Effect of iron deficiency anemia on the levels of hemoglobin A1c in nondiabetic patients. *Acta Haematol*. 2004; 112:126–128. doi: 10.1159/000079722. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar] [Ref list]
- Basil A. Alzahrani, Hassan K. Salamatullah, Faisal S. Alsharm, et al, The effect of different types of anemia on HbA1c levels in non-diabetics, *BMC Endocrine Disorders* volume 23, Article number: 24 (2023)
- Shanthi B, Revathy C, ArcotJagdeeshwaran Manjula Devi S. Effect of iron deficiency on glycation of haemoglobin in nondiabetics. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*. 2013 Jan; 7(1):15.
- Christy AL, Manjrekar PA, Babu RP, Hegde A, MS R. Influence of iron deficiency anemia on hemoglobin A1c levels in diabetic individuals with controlled plasma glucose levels. *Iranian biomedical journal*. 2014 Apr; 18(2):88.
- El-Agouza I, Abu Shohla A, Sirdah M. The effect of iron deficiency anaemia on the levels of haemoglobin subtypes: possible consequences for clinical diagnosis. *Clin Lab Haematol*. 2002; 24:285–289.
- Sinha N, Mishra TK, Singh T, Gupta N. Effect of iron deficiency anemia on hemoglobin A1c levels. *Ann Lab Med*. 2012 Jan; 32(1):17-22 doi:10.3343/alm.2012.32.1.17. Epub 2011 Dec 20. PMID: 22259774; PMCID: PMC3255499.
- Rai KB, Pattabiraman TN. Glycosylated haemoglobin levels in iron deficiency anemia. *Indian J Med Res*. 1986 Feb; 83:234–6.
- Tarim O, Küçükdoğan A, Günay U, Eralp O, Ercan I. Effects of iron deficiency anemia on hemoglobin A1c in type 1 diabetes mellitus. *Pediatr Int*. 1999 Aug; 41(4):357–62.
- Hashimoto K, Noguchi S, Morimoto Y, Hamada S, Wasada K, Imai S, et al. A1C but Not Serum Glycated Albumin Is Elevated in Late Pregnancy Owing to Iron. *Diabetes*. 2008; 31(3):31–4
- Shimizu I, Hiramatsu Y, Omori Y, Nakabayashi M, JGA (Japan Glycated

- Albumin) Study Group. Comparison of HbA1c and glycated albumin as a control marker for newborn complications in diabetic women in a multicentre study in Japan (Japan glycated albumin study group: study 2). *Annals of Clinical Biochemistry*. 2018; 55: 639–646
24. Sharifi F, Sazandeh SH. Serum ferritin in type 2 diabetes mellitus and its relationship with HbA1c. *Acta Medica Iranica*. 2004; 42(2):142–5.
25. Koga M., Saito H., Mukai M., Matsumoto S., Kasayama S. Influence of iron metabolism indices on glycated haemoglobin but not glycated albumin levels in premenopausal women. *Acta Diabetol*. 2010; 47:S65–S69. doi: 10.1007/s00592-009-0123-6.
26. Sankar Kalairajan, Vijaya Durairaj K., Malathy A. R. A study on influence of iron deficiency anaemia over HbA1c levels *International Journal of Advances in Medicine* | July-August 2019 | Vol 6 | Issue 4 pISSN 2349-3925 | eISSN 2349-3933
27. Raj S, Rajan GV. Correlation between elevated serum ferritin and HbA1c in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Int J Res Med Sci*. 2013; 1(1):12–15.
28. Omar E Fadlseed., Ishag Adam2, Duria A Rayis3, Gasim I Gasim Serum Ferritin, Iron Deficiency Anemia and Hemoglobin A1c in Non-diabetic Pregnant Women DOI: 10.7860/JCDR/2019/41721.12984
29. Alap L. Christy, Poornima A. Manjrekar, Ruby P. Babu, Anupama Hegde, and Rukmini M.S. Influence of Iron Deficiency Anemia on Hemoglobin A1C Levels in Diabetic Individuals with Controlled Plasma Glucose Levels *Iranian Biomedical Journal* 18 (2): 88-93 (April 2014)DOI: 10.6091/ibj.1257.2014.